

Peanut proteins in selective sensing of Bi^{III} at trace concentrations

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Abstract : Bismuth is an environmentally significant element due to its usefulness in different aspects of life especially in semiconductors, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries. It is less soluble in aqueous medium so it is poorly absorbed in human cells, however it plays a crucial role in various diseases mainly gastrointestinal disorders and neurological disorders. In this report selective recognition of trace concentration of bismuth is observed with peanut proteins conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin, which are available from cheap source and their extraction is cost effective too. For avoiding bismuth precipitation, we have optimized the pH of the solutions and they were subjected to spectrophotometric analysis. Absorption, fluorescence, circular dichroism and Raman spectra support the interaction of bismuth with peanut proteins.

Keywords : Peanut, bismuth, sensing, absorbance, fluorescence, circular dichroism, Raman spectra.

Introduction

Designing new organic molecules for the sensing of biologically important and environmentally hazardous metal ions at trace concentration levels is an exciting research in recent years^{1,2}. Some metals are of environmental concern as they cause various health hazards including carcinogenicity while some others have useful applications. Among transition-metal ions, mercury is the most dangerous cation for the environment. Being highly reactive to biological molecules, it enters the living cells causing prenatal brain damage, serious cognitive disorders and minamata diseases³⁻⁶. Lead is known to be a larger problem for children than it is for adults at higher concentrations. Brain damage and nervous disorders are the most common outcomes of high level lead exposure⁷. Studies also indicate that lead accumulation inhibits plant growth due to denaturation of proteinaceous enzymes that control cellular processes⁸. Antimony and its compounds are however milder in causing acute human health effects, with the exception of antimony potassium tartrate, a prodrug used to treat leishmaniasis.

They rather have medical applications and are used in antiprotozoan drugs^{9,10}. Thallium (Tl⁺) is known to cause isomorphous replacements with potassium in biological systems and activate some enzymes as a consequence. Sometimes this poses a threat as the thallium ion may bind more strongly than potassium to a site and then fail to bind additional sites as required for the biological activity. Thallium actively concentrates in mitochondria of the cell and thereby interferes in oxidative phosphorylation¹¹. ²⁰¹Tl radioisotopes are however potential candidates for heart imaging¹². Bismuth is present at trace concentration (8 µg/kg) in earth's crust. It is used in our daily lives in semiconductors, cosmetic products, medicines (for treatment of syphilis, peptic ulcers and dermatological disorders), alloys, catalyst in the chemical industry, metallurgical additives, and preparation and recycling of uranium in nuclear fuels¹³. ²¹²Bi and ²¹³Bi isotopes have been used for cancer treatment^{14,15}. However bismuth causes several toxic effects in human body such as nephropathy, osteoarthropathy, hepatitis and neuropathology when present at high concentrations¹⁶.

Spectroscopic techniques e.g. atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS)¹⁷, hydride generation-atomic fluorescence spectrometry (HG-AFS)¹⁸, inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES)¹⁹, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)²⁰ and electrochemical methods²¹ have been used for detecting bismuth in several samples at trace concentrations. These methods however need costly instrumentation and rigorous sample preparation techniques.

To the best of our knowledge reports on metal ion sensing using natural bioactive polymers like plant proteins are still lacking in the literature. Peanuts represent cheap and widely available source of plant proteins growing all over the world. In this report we have developed a spectrophotometric method of bismuth sensing using the peanut protein fractions conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin selectively out of other heavy metals like Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Sb^{III} and Tl^{III} in a very convenient and cost effective way.

Experimental

Materials : Sodium citrate and citric acid were obtained from Fischer Scientific for buffer preparation. Bi(NO₃)₃, Tl(NO₃)₃, Pb(NO₃)₂, HgCl₂, K₂Sb₂(C₄H₂O₆)₂ salts were taken from Merck. All the solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. Peanuts were purchased from the local market. For the determination of protein concentration, the components of Bradford reagent i.e. CH₃CH₂OH, H₃PO₄, NaOH, CH₃OH were obtained from Merck. Coomassie brilliant blue G was obtained from HIMEDIA and all the other chemicals in this experiment were of analytical grade.

Apparatus : The pH of the solutions was maintained using the pH/ion meter (S 220-K) of Mettler. The absorption spectra were measured using Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer and fluorescence spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer LS-55 spectrofluorimeter equipped with a quartz cell with a 1.0 cm optical path length. The excitation and emission slits of the monochromator were adjusted to 5 nm. RAM HR, Jobin Yvon spectrometer and a Peltier-

cooled charge-coupled-device (CCD) detector was used for the determination of the Raman vibrational frequencies of the experimental samples. The far-UV CD spectra were obtained using JASCO J-815 spectropolarimeter.

Methods

The extraction, purification and characterization of the peanut protein fractions conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin were done using the methods described in the earlier report²². The obtained protein fractions were characterized using the absorption spectra and SDS-PAGE pattern. The maximum absorption intensity of conarachin II at 278 nm, conarachin I at 265 nm and arachin at 280 nm, agrees with the literature data. The SDS-PAGE pattern of conarachin II, and arachin show molecular weight bands at 39800, 33100, 26900, 24000, 21900, 18600, 15800 Da and 72400, 60300, 39800, 33100, 26900, 21900 Da and conarachin I shows a single band at 18600 Da. The concentration of the proteins was measured using Bradford reagents²³. The concentration of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin were 0.9, 0.8 and 0.76 mg/mL respectively.

Absorption and fluorescence spectra :

Absorption and fluorescence study were used to determine the selectivity and sensitivity of peanut proteins in the presence of various heavy metal ions, such as Bi^{III}, Tl^{III}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II} and Sb^{III}. The salt solutions (1 mM each) of Bi(NO₃)₃, Tl(NO₃)₃, Pb(NO₃)₂, HgCl₂, K₂Sb₂(C₄H₂O₆)₂ were prepared with triple distilled water. For preparation of Bi(NO₃)₃ solution a weighed amount of the salt was first dissolved in a drop of HNO₃ and then diluted with water to required volume. This was done to avoid precipitation of Bi as its oxynitrate directly in water medium. To identify the possible complexation, 0.3 mL each of these metal ion solutions was mixed with 0.2 mL of protein solutions and volume was made up to 1.5 mL with 0.1 M sodium citrate-citric acid buffer of pH 3. To optimize the Bi-protein complexation, 1 mM bismuth(III) solution was added to the protein solution in different stoichiometric ratios. The solutions were subjected to absorption and fluorescence spectral studies. The experi-

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ment was also studied at the pHs 5.6, 6.7 and 7.9 of 0.1 mM phosphate buffer medium. But due to the metal hydroxide precipitation, the experiment was done at pH 3 of 0.1 mM citrate buffer medium.

Circular dichroism (CD) spectra :

To obtain CD spectra, 1 mM Bi^{III} solution was added to the 50 μ L of protein solution in a quartz cylindrical cuvette of 0.1 cm path-length at 25 °C in different stoichiometric ratios. The final spectra have been taken after three consecutive scans and base line correction.

Raman spectra :

The Raman spectra of the different peanut protein fractions were compared with the protein-Bi^{III} complexes. 20 μ L of different peanut proteins and the solutions of protein-Bi^{III} complexes were taken on glass plate coated with Al foil. The solutions were dried in vacuum desiccator over night. Then the samples were then taken for Raman spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra : Conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin, show the absorption maxima at 278, 265 and 280 nm respectively. The absorption data (Fig. 1) suggest the selective interaction of Bi^{III} ions with all the three proteins. With increasing Bi concentrations in the protein solutions a gradual increase in the absorbance of the three peanut proteins were observed. From the absorbance data we have calculated the binding constant and free energy changes upon complexation using Benesi-Hildebrand equation²².

$$\frac{1}{A - A_0} = \frac{1}{A_1 - A_0} + \frac{1}{(A_1 - A_0)K[M]} \quad (1)$$

$$Y = A + BX \quad (2)$$

where A is the absorbance of the experimental solution containing metal and protein. A_0 is the absorbance of the protein only. A_1 is the absorbance when protein is completely bound with the metal. $[M]$ is the metal ion concentration. K is the binding/association constant.

Eq. (1) can be represented as eq. (2) which is a

Fig. 1. Plot of absorbance of conarachin II, conarachin I, arachin with different metal ions at pH 3 in citrate buffer (0.1 M) medium.

Fig. 2. Benesi-Hildebrand plot of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin-Bi^{III} complexes at pH 3.

Table 1. Some physical parameters of Bi^{III} complexes of the protein fractions

Complex	Binding constant (M ⁻¹)	Free energy change (kJ/mol)	Stoichiometric ratios
Conarachin II-Bi ^{III}	2.4737×10^3	-19.488	1 : 1
Conarachin I-Bi ^{III}	3.7614×10^3	-20.533	1 : 1
Arachin-Bi ^{III}	0.92623×10^3	-17.038	1 : 1

straight line having intercept $1/(A_1 - A_0)$ and slope $1/(A_1 - A_0)K$. From the Benesi-Hildebrand (BH) plot (Fig. 2), we have calculated the binding constant values. Corresponding free energy change (ΔG) values were calculated at a temperature (T) of 298 K using the equation

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad (3)$$

Binding constant, free energy change and stoichiometric ratio (obtained from the BH plot) of the three peanut protein-bismuth complexes are tabulated in Table 1.

The binding constants of the conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin-Bi complexes are, $2.4737 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $3.7614 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $0.92623 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ respectively. The ΔG values upon complexation of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin with Bi are -19.488 kJ/mol, -20.533 kJ/mol and -17.038 kJ/mol respectively. The greater value of binding constant and more negative value of free energy change indicate the highest interaction of conarachin I with Bi^{III} amongst the three proteins.

Fluorescence spectra : The emission maxima for conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin, were observed at 365 nm, 425 nm and 340 nm respectively. Fluorescence spectra also support the selective interaction of Bi^{III} with the three peanut proteins as compared to other heavy metals like Tl^{III}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II} and Sb^{III}. Figs. 3, 4 and 5 reflect this selective behavior of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin respectively. With increasing bismuth concentration emission intensity decreases which, indicates the interaction of Bi^{III} with three proteins. The plot (Fig. 6) F_0/F versus $[\text{Bi}^{\text{III}}]$ shows a curved nature which suggests that the fluorescence quenching is both static and dynamic type indicating both ground state and excited state complexations of the proteins with Bi^{III}.

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of conarachin II in presence of different heavy metals at pH 3 ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 278 \text{ nm}$).

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of conarachin I in presence of different heavy metals at pH 3 ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 265 \text{ nm}$).

CD spectra : The far UV CD spectra (Figs. 7, 8 and 9) of the three peanut proteins showed two minima at 208 and 222 nm which indicates α helical structures of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin. With in-

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Fig. 5. Fluorescence spectra of arachin in presence of different heavy metals at pH 3 ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm).

Fig. 6. Stern-Volmer plot of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin-Bi^{III} complexes at pH 3.

Fig. 7. CD spectra of conarachin II with varying concentrations of Bi^{III}.

Fig. 8. CD spectra of conarachin I with varying concentrations of Bi^{III}.

Fig. 9. CD spectra of arachin with varying concentrations of Bi^{III}.

creasing bismuth concentration, the gradual decrease of ellipticity indicates the lower value of α helical content in the protein molecules which leads to the formation of β sheet structures in all the three proteins. The change in the circular dichroism spectra of the three proteins upon interaction with bismuth clearly indicates the modification of the secondary structure of the proteins.

Raman study : Upon interaction with Bi, a large number of vibrational frequencies were observed (Fig. 10 and Table 2) to appear or disappear for the three proteins conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin. The vibrational frequency near 1000 cm^{-1} indicates the pres-

Fig. 10. Raman spectra of peanut proteins with Bi^{III}.

Table 2. Details of the Raman spectral data

	Raman modes (cm ⁻¹)					
	Conarachin II	Conarachin II-Bi ^{III}	Conarachin I	Conarachin I-Bi ^{III}	Arachin	Arachin-Bi ^{III}
C-C-C out of plane bending						323
C-C-C out of plane skeletal deformation	–	380	400	390	–	371
C-C-C out of plane bending	457	455	455	–	475	–
C-C-C out of plane bending	466	–	–	–	–	–
C-C-C inplane skeletal deformation	–	520	538	530	557	570
N-H ₂ wagging	615	620	625	620	619	–
Tyr	636	630	–	–	–	–
Tyr	–	830	–	822	829	811
Trp	–	900	884	897	–	–
C-H out of plane bending	–	945	–	939	920	930
C-N-H ₂ stretching	976	989	975	–	990	–
Phe	995	1000	1000	–	1000	–
C-C, C-N and C-O stretching mode	1075	1075	1091	1050	–	–
C-C stretching mode	1130	–	–	–	–	–
Tyr, Phe	1197	–	–	1190	1171	–
Amide III	–	1260	1264	1260	1260	–
CH ₂ deformation	–	1427	–	1425	1451	–
Phe	–	–	–	1617	1607	–
Trp	–	–	–	–	1630	–
Amide 1, β-sheet	–	–	–	–	1666	–

ence of phenylalanine in the three proteins. C-C-C out of plane bending and C-N-H₂ stretching were shifted for conarachin II, but were disappeared for conarachin I and arachin. Shifting of the peak positions near 630 cm⁻¹ and 830 cm⁻¹ for tyrosine and 900 cm⁻¹ for tryptophan²⁴⁻²⁷ in the three proteins indicates the interaction of bismuth with peanut proteins. Raman spectra also suggest that the interaction of the three peanut proteins with bismuth is due to the presence of tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine in the side chain of the protein molecules. This observation is also in agreement with individual interactions of Bi^{III} with the three aromatic amino acids, tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine²⁸.

Conclusion

Peanut proteins were subjected to interaction with different heavy metal ions and the solutions were analyzed using different spectral techniques. Absorption, fluorescence, circular dichroism and Raman spectra indicate the preferential interaction of peanut proteins with bismuth amongst the heavy metals mercury, thallium, lead, bismuth and antimony. The results reveal the stoichiometric ratio of peanut protein-Bi^{III} complex is 1 : 1 for all the three cases. The greater value of binding constant and free energy change supports the highest interaction of conarachin I with bismuth. The Raman spectra also indicate the presence of three amino acids tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine in the side chain of the three peanut proteins. The modification in the secondary structure of conarachin II, conarachin I and arachin obtained from the circular dichroism spectra are due to the interaction of bismuth with three amino acids tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine within the protein molecules. The results strongly support a selective sensing of Bi^{III} amongst a series of heavy metals at their trace concentrations.

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